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JOSEP MOSES JURAN – THE FATHER OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. Some years ago, I realized that many graduates of the Faculty of Electromechanics of Craiova, as it was called back then, were able to find a job in the quality management departments. It was a new domain for most people. The employers preferred young employees in this new domain, and, unfortunately, they were not taught about this domain during their academic studies. I proposed a new post-academic course and I had a lot of success. I consider this course has been successful because we had and we still have a lot of candidates. I also consider that the idea has been successful because this course has turned into a quality management (QM) programme which is still very attractive. Within this context I discovered the father of the quality management: Joseph Moses Juran, born in Romania.

Keywords: *Josep Moses Juran, quality, quality management, academic studies.*

Rezumat. Cu câțiva ani în urmă, mi-am dat seama că mulți absolvenți ai Facultății de Electromecanică din Craiova, așa cum se numea pe atunci, au putut găsi un loc de muncă în departamentele de management al calității. Era un domeniu nou pentru majoritatea oamenilor. Angajatorii au preferat angajați tineri în acest nou domeniu, dar, din păcate, tinerii aceștia nu au studiat acest domeniu în timpul studiilor academice. În acest sens, am propus un nou curs post-academic și am avut mult succes. Consider că acest curs a avut succes, deoarece am avut și avem încă mulți candidați. De asemenea, consider că ideea a avut succes, deoarece acest curs s-a transformat într-un program de management al calității care este încă foarte atractiv. În acest context, l-am descoperit pe tatăl managementului calității: Joseph Moses Juran, născut în România.

Cuvinte-cheie: *Josep Moses Juran, calitate, managementul calității, studii academice.*

The road to success was difficult

Josep Moses Juran was born in Brăila on the 24th of December 1904 . At the age of three, in 1907, he moved with his family at Gura Humorului, which was part of the Austrian-Hungarian Empire. He lived there until the age of 8. His father, a shoemaker, left in 1909 in the USA for a better life, and after three years, his family formed of his wife Gitel and three children named Joseph, Nathan and Minerva, went after him and the whole family moved in Minneapolis, Minnesota state, at the border with Canada. They left for a better life, but at

the beginning they changed their little clay house, surrounded by flowers from Gura Humorului, for a wooden shed covered in cardboard, surrounded by the forests near Minneapolis. They lacked both water and electricity just as in Moldova. Shoemakers couldn't find work too easily because the shoes were produced in factories. In these conditions, the child Juran had several unqualified jobs, accepting any activity needed in the community they lived in. He worked as a horse janitor, bootblack, shop-assistant at the grocer's and accountant. On top of all these, he was also devastated by his mother's death when he was only 16. After many years, he declared: "We grew up without being afraid of working hard, many hours, every day. He learnt from this experience that we had to use any opportunity and that one could learn from any error or failure. We accepted the responsibility to make ourselves a safe future. The ethical principles have been useful all our lives". In 1920, at the age of 16, Juran enlisted at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering of the University Minnesota. He paid his studies by himself with the money he earned. At university he discovered the CHESS, activity which changed considerably his life. His very developed analytic spirit allowed him to discover the subtleties and the implications of this old intelligent game. He became the champion of his university, he got excellent results in the competitions organized in Minnesota State and he experienced his colleagues' admiration and the pride to be respected for your own achievements. In 1924 he graduated the Faculty of Engineering, and in 1936 he got his Ph.D. degree in law at the *Loyole University Chicago School of Law*. After graduation, he got a job within the Department of Inspection of the Western Electric Company. In 1928 he published a booklet entitled "Statistical Methods applied to manufacturing problems" where he presented the method of dividing in order to evaluate the manufacturing quality, and the principles written in this book are used even today.

How quality has appeared

During World War Two, Juran was in charge with the manufacturing of the military equipment delivered to the Soviet and British allies. He noticed that 80% of the defects were determined by only 20% of the causes that led to rejects, and starting from here, he formulated "The Pareto Principle" which he extended later on the sales when he realized that 20% of the customers made 80% of the whole profit. After the war, he was asked by the Japanese to help them improve their reputation as "manufacturers of rejects". They were very convinced that they needed a change and for this they totally accepted Juran's ideas about quality assurance. Among other things, they set up "quality committees" which had an important impact on the human relationships although their contribution to the product quality was of about 10%. In a short period of time, Japan became an economic superpower due to the quality of its goods and, as an acknowledgement of Juran's contribution to the initiation of the Japanese miracle, the Emperor of Japan awarded him *The Order of the Sacred Treasure*. In 1951 he published the book **Quality Control Handbook** which established his reputation as the father of quality together with Deming. Juran defines the quality as **utility of usage, not a simple conformation to the specifications**. Juran also take into account the

customer, especially his necessities. The trilogy of quality, “**Quality Planning, Quality control and Quality Improvement**”, is well-known as an important contribution to the quality assurance. The first part of the trilogy is preoccupied by the identification of the customer, the product requirements and the prioritization of the business objectives. The second part implies the use of the statistic control methods. The third part refers to Juran’s conviction that the quality improvement must be continuous. Juran added the social dimension that is necessary to the statistic quality control, having an essential contribution to what we call today “*Total Quality Management*”.

In Bucovina again

In 1972 he came back in Romania for a short visit to la *Tractorul* Company of Braşov. He also travelled to Gura Humorului: *“I lived here for five years before emigrating to America at the age of eight. At Gura Humorului, the house I lived in does not exist anymore.... But the Carpathians I used to climb as a child and the water of Moldavia River with its wonderful fish are still there. There is something else still strongly rooted in Gura Humorului, “the village spirit”. Bucovina is a profoundly rural area, and its inhabitants have a robust character due to the fact that they have to earn their living against unfriendly nature. This “struggle” requires hard work, honesty and a powerful feeling of human solidarity”.*

In 1992, when he was elected honorary member of the Romanian Academy abroad, he said: *“I am, of course, grateful to all the honours I received from the Romanian institutions. I am also aware of the fact that the Romanians endured a lot of difficult years and that the way ahead is long and difficult. But I also know that, after so many years of experience, the achievement of quality is a vital element in building a prosperous economy”.*

In 1994, when he turned 90, at the request of the Romanian Society for Quality Assurance, he uttered the following message: *“ I wish to use his opportunity to personally greet the Romanian. As you may know, I was born in Romania and I spent my childhood there until I emigrated in America at the age of eight. I grew up as an American, but I kept my childhood memories about my roots. I had the chance to visit Romania twice and I visited the places where I lived - Brăila și Gura Humorului. These visits were very emotional experiences for me.”*

In 1998, he accepted, on the request of some personalities from Romania, that the Romanian Prize for Quality to be named after him and to be awarded yearly, from 2000, by the “J.M. Juran Romanian Prize for Quality” Foundation to the persons and companies with excellent results in the implementation of the quality principles.

He died on the 28th of February 2008, in New York. Despite his age of 103, he was in complete control of all his faculties until the very end.

Reference

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